

An Improved Collaborative Pruning Using Ant Colony Optimization and Pessimistic Technique of C5.0 Decision Tree Algorithm

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Abstract

Decision Tree (DT) classification algorithms are sensitive instruments used to excavate hidden patterns in the heart of data. The major problem of the algorithms is overfitting; a situation where unwanted patterns are represented. However, the majority of prior researchers have worked on improving DT classification efficiencies with different pruning strategies. This paper presents a collaborative pruning model to improve on the classification efficiency of DTs. The model generates two forests using gain ratio: virgin and pessimistic pruned forest. Both were subjected to optimization with Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) and the rules extracted were accumulated with optimization values. Similar groups and unproductive rules were trimmed at once to reduce the size of the tree. Comparatively, the model consistently outperformed other DT classification algorithms employed, with the smallest tree size and almost perfect classification. Besides, it had a better accuracy of 0.98% than the closest C5.0 DT algorithm, especially in a relatively big dataset.

Keywords—Decision Tree, Ant Colony, Pheromone trails, Rule-based, Forest

1.0 Introduction

In the era of big data, classification algorithms are the dominant data mining tool to unravel different patterns in the dataset structures. It could be an invaluable instrument in the hand of Management, Health Workers as well as Teachers to make the right decision when faced with issues that can affect life or property. There are various classification algorithms, some of which are Decision Tree (DT), Support Vector Machines (SVMs), Artificial Neural Network and others. However, according to Cai (2006) and Han *et al.*, (2011) the decision tree has been adjudged the most explicit, simple, comprehensible and faster to construct. These qualities are of great importance to experts.

Quinlan (1983) came up with a DT classification algorithm known as Iterative Dichomizer 3 (ID3) which has since been found to be the bedrock of most common but efficient prediction algorithms. A popular classifier algorithm software; Waikato Environment for Knowledge Analysis (WEKA) has some classifiers built from a modified version of ID3. The trees generated by ID3 potentially lead to overfitting due to unnecessary growth and duplication of branches (Han, *et al.*, 2011). A technique was then introduced known as pruning, which has potential to improve generalization of the decisions trees and reduce the size. Researchers have introduced many strategies to decrease *the* negative effects of overfitting on prediction which has led to various classifiers including J48, CART, C4.5, and C5.0 and others (Ashari *et al.*, 2013, Freitas *et al.*, 2010; Hssina *et al.*, 2014; Jadhav and Channe, 2016; Luna, *et al.*, 2019, Nakamura, 2019; Polaka, *et al.*, 2010). However, in this paper, we intend to introduce a novel collaborative pruning technique in order to improve on the classification accuracy of the Decision Tree (DT) algorithm.

The rest of this paper is organised as follows. The next section is the literature review of Decision Tree Classification Algorithms and their problems. Section 3 describes the proposed method of pruning. In section 4 the experimental results are discussed. Finally, section 5 provides some conclusions.

2.0 Theoretical Concepts and Related Works

2.1 Major Problems in Classification Algorithms

The major problem that Bramer (2002) observed in classification algorithms is the effect of unwanted instances included in the historical dataset known as overfitting (noisy data) in training data. The consequences, which result in a bias termed as overfitting avoidance bias (Wolpert, 1992, Fürnkranz, 1997). Sometimes, the presence of noise in training data adds to the numbers of attributes which in turn increase computational cost and equally reduce the model efficiency in term of accurate prediction of unseen instances (Liu, 2015).

Iorio, *et al.*, (2019) opined that popular decision tree methods like C4.5, J48 and C5.0 are accurate and efficient, but often faced with the problem of generating very large trees that make them complex to experts and sometimes biased in operation during classification procedure towards attribute with large values. Moreover, classification methods such as Rule-based are outstanding in performance especially in some application domains but not spared from the problem of overfitting that slowed down the success of the model (Al-Behadili *et al.* 2018).

In the work of Otero *et al.*, (2013), building a model that takes full advantage of the predictive accuracy is one of the core goals of a classification algorithm—i.e., the number of correct predictions divided by the total number of predictions—in the test set, while in some application domains clarity of the model plays an important role (Freitas, Wieser *et al.*, 2010 and Dhar, Chou *et al.*, 2000).

2.2 Pruning Techniques

The decision tree is a classification model that mimics the natural tree structure (Jiawei Han and Micheline Kamber, 2001). Although the decision tree sometimes generates unwanted and meaningless rules as it grows deeper. To make the tree to perform optimally a strategy was introduced called pruning. Pruning is a mechanism that avoids a large tree but improves the classification accuracy of any classification algorithm where it is implemented (Patil *et al.*, 2010).

There are two main pruning methods; Post-pruning and Pre-pruning as mentioned by Patil Lathi *et al.*, 2012). According to Patel and Aluvalu (2014), Tapio Elomaa and Matti Kääriäinen, (2001) “Training accuracy for simplicity is the hallmark of pruning”. The process of cutting off non-predictive parts of a model is called “Pruning” According to Merriam-Webster’s dictionary (2020), to prune means, “to cut away what is unwanted or superfluous”. Practically, many real-world datasets are noisy - they contain a degree of uncertainty that is either inherent in the domain or results from how the data is collected, or both. Sometimes the sources of the raw datasets are from heterogeneous sources that form the data warehouse.

2.3 Ant Colony Optimization

There are heuristic biology-inspired algorithms in the field of Machine Learning particularly in data mining found to be successful when applied to classifier algorithms. Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) technique is one of those algorithms discovered some years back as a good procedure to solve the optimisation problem in classification models (Vesterstrom and Thomsen 2004, Minnaert and Martens 2014, Javidy, *et al.* 2015). It has shown a considerable

power in identifying and mining of optimised rules from classification model processes. Rules excavated from these operations through ACO algorithms are found to be simple to express in natural language and enhance simplicity of the models, thereby improving its predictive ability (Minnaert and Martens 2014, Liang, Guo *et. al.*, 2017).

Similarly, Ant Colony Optimization (ACO) as seen by Dorigo and Caro (1999), Dorigo and Stutzle (2004), are algorithms that have been successfully applied to discover a list of IF-THEN classification rules. It is seen as an algorithm that is self-organized and capable of undertaking complex tasks by having their individual ants interact with one another and their environment. Communication in the colonies are indirect between the ants, hence, this demonstrates the intelligent behaviour of the ants. The pheromone concentration of a path influences the choices ants make, and the more pheromones, the more attractive a path becomes. (Otero *et. al.*, 2013).

2.4 Related Works

Parpinelli *et. al.*, (2002) were inspired by the ant colony optimization algorithm to avoid overfitting in which the prediction rules are complex and consist of a large number of terms. This process consists of three main procedures, which are: rule construction, rule pruning (threshold values), and pheromone updating. The pruning approach is that a rule list is generated through the accumulation of rule extractions; when an instance satisfies the rule antecedent (if-part) and the rule consequence (then-part) is then removed from the training set. This process will require all terms to be visited irrespective of its contribution to the overall performance of the algorithm.

In an attempt to further improve classification accuracy, Wahid and Al-Mazini (2018) introduced another algorithm developed using Java programming language and Ant-miner technique. It is a supervised learning algorithm that employed a separate training and the test sets. Five-fold cross-validation was used on the training sets. The pheromone was initially set to 0 and different rules were induced in the repeated loop. The cases that adequately represented were removed from the training set. Each rule generated is pruned during the looping and the pheromone value is made to increase. The process of pruning takes along time and consumed more computing resources though had improved accuracy.

According to Luna *et. al.*, (2019), pruning method using an additive tree (AddTree) strategy for building decision trees was considered. Each branch from the root to a leaf stands as the outcome of a gradient boosted ensemble for a group of the instance space. Subsequently, AdditiveTree was made to produce a new model when CART and gradient boosted stumps (GBS) are bridged. At the visitation of each node, a weak learner was found using gradient boosting on the whole dataset instead of using the only dataset left in the training to determine the next split. The hybrid model outperforms CART in terms of accuracy and interpretability despite its weakness in producing a simple tree which resulted in underfitting.

Elgibreen and Aksoy (2013) proposed another improvement in rule-induction to enhance classification accuracy and comprehensibility. Usually, when searching for the best rule, a rule is induced starting from an empty one, then a specialisation process begins to create more specialized rules from the seed example. Meanwhile, the goal was to improve the accuracy of rule induction, but it consumes a lot of time and needs special pruning procedures to stop the search and reduce its space. Moreover, it is difficult to decide what to specialise and when to stop.

In the work of Jiang *et. al.* (2017), Forest pruning Based on branch importance was introduced, they tried to introduce an ensemble pruning method with the view to examining

the importance of tree branches to the performance of the whole ensemble using a novel proposed metric called ‘importance gain’. The importance of a branch is designed by considering ensemble accuracy and the diversity of ensemble members, and thus the metric reasonably evaluates how much improvement of the ensemble accuracy can be achieved when a branch is pruned. The process seems good but was found to be complex and have extended time of prediction.

3.0 Methodology

The methodology adopted in this study is best illustrated in Figure 1. The figure captured the main goal of this research work. The dataset for the work was subjected to pre-processing and thereafter fed into the algorithm to build two main forests with the minimum of 10 decision trees (n); pruned forest with pessimistic pruning technique of C5.0 algorithm and a virgin forest, a forest without any pruning mechanism except the use of entropy and gain ratio theories to determine the feature impurity as well as the level of information available in the attributes and the features. Ant Colony Optimisation method is introduced to the forests for extraction of optimised rules with the principle of confusion matrix. The rules are later dropped into the accumulator for filtering (Pruning) to reduce the size of the rules which invariably form the final model.

Figure 1: Generic Architecture of Collaborative Pruning Model CPM

Algorithm 1 runs through the process of building the forests from the data space of D which is split into 10-cross validation set d . As stated in Figure 1, the algorithm selects each feature and attribute with the best value D_{best} , d_{best} of Shannon's entropy and Gain ratio theories

which check the level of impurity and amount information available from them. The construction of tree T_v , A_D stops when all attributes contain the same class (pure) or there is no more feature or attribute left.

Algorithm 1: The Collaborative Pruning Model CPM Forests Building Algorithm

1. **Input:** an attribute valued dataset D
2. **Output :** pruned rules
3. **If** D s have the same class "pure" OR empty then
4. *terminate*
5. **end if**
6. **for all** attribute $d \in D$ **do;**
7. **if** $d =$ *splitting feature* **then**
8. *Compute information theoretic criteria*
9. **end if**
10. **end for**
11. $D_{best} \leftarrow$ *Best attribute selected according to Shannon theories of impurity*
12. $Tree \leftarrow$ *Create a decision node that tests d_{best} in the root*
13. $D_v \leftarrow$ *Induced children from D based on d_{best}*
14. **for all** D_v **do**
15. $Tree_v \leftarrow$ *C5.0 (D_v);*
16. *Induced the rule with C5.0 $Tree_v$ and validate them*
17. $Tree \leftarrow$ *ID3+Gain Ratio (D_v) without Pruning*
16. *Induced the rule ID3+Gain Ratio+ ACO algorithm using confusion matrix principle*
18. *Accumulate the rules from the corresponding branches of both Trees A_D*
19. **end for**
20. **for each** rule A_D **do;**
21. *Run filter algorithm by evaluation*
22. **end for**
23. **Return** *pruned rules*

This study was on Collaborative Pruning Model (CPM) with the sole intention of exploiting the strength of both algorithms to produce an efficient boosting model.

The CPM trained the instances on 70% of the original instances of each dataset and used the remaining 30% to test the performance of the model. The model further partitioned the training set into 10 to obtain 10-fold segments. Each fold was recursively partitioned further to 95% training and 5% validation as illustrated in Figure 1. The two techniques used to build the forests as found in the figure were made to generate trees (forest) for each partitioned training dataset. The first technique, C5.0 model used gain ratio information theory to construct its tree and identify the weaker subtrees for pruning to improve the model's outputs. The binomial distribution principle ($\epsilon'(T,S) = \epsilon(T,S) + \frac{|leaves(T)|}{2 \cdot |S|}$) which was found to be too optimistic was used along with confidence interval theory ($\epsilon'(\text{pruned}(T,t),S) \leq \epsilon'(T,S) + \sqrt{\frac{\epsilon(T,S) \cdot (1-\epsilon(T,S))}{|S|}}$). This later theory was introduced as a pessimistic concept to fine-tune the excessive optimistic error rate of early theory.

Each partitioned model was validated using the remaining 5% with ACO keeping tracks of the performance of each tree to further establish the viability of the path. Consequently, virgin (raw) trees were generated to form a forest as the second technique because no pruning mechanism was used in the construction except gain ratio theory. The forest optimisation was also done with Ant Colony Optimisation technique to ascertain the detracted performance subtrees and allow the model to fully express its potential based on the available branches before optimisation. The constructed subtrees were also validated with the validation set. Both forests from the two models were converted to their equivalent rules and stored in the accumulator for filtering according to their performance with ACO inline with a confusion matrix concept.

The study used Information Gain Ratio (Gain Ratio (ai,S) = $\frac{InformationGain(ai,S)}{Entropy(ai,S)}$) in both models to overcome the problem of favouring any feature together with feature selection using Shannon's Entropy Theory (Entropy (y,S) = $\sum_{c_j \in dom(y)} - \frac{|σy=c_jS|}{|S|} \cdot \frac{\log_2|σy=c_jS|}{|S|}$) application. The pheromone trail value was updated at each visit of a branch or rule by increasing its pheromone value by 1, the total value is compared with the number of visits.

The accuracy of predictions; $\frac{TP+FP}{TP+FP+TN+FN}$ % that is, the true positive is divided by the total number of visit multiplied by hundred to get a percentage of accuracy and vice versa for false-positive. Each path was then classified as being efficient or unproductive. The model did not throw away the so-called less efficient or unproductive rules but accumulated all along with their percentage of performance into a pool with the rules from both C5.0 and ACO algorithms. The accumulator was then processed by selecting only the rules that increased accuracy.

3.1 Dataset

Table 1: **The cancer dataset used for the experiments:**

Repository's Source	Quantity	Class
University of Wisconsin Hospitals, Madison (UCI)	2,000	Benign and Malignant

The attributes in the instances were 10; code number, Clump Thickness, Uniformity of Cell Size, Uniformity of Cell Shape, Marginal Adhesion, Single Epithelial Cell Size, Bare Nuclei, Bland Chromatin, Normal Nucleoli and they were all nominal attributes.

The 2,000 instances used contained 1,300 benign that represent those samples that were not cancerous and 700 malignant which were cancerous samples. The 70% of the original samples which was 1,400 were designated for the training of the model while the remaining 30% (600) were used for the test.

However, in each forest of 10 trees, 95% of 1,400 (1,330) was used to build the tree and the remaining 5% (70) of the samples were used for validation by ACO during optimisation.

3.2 Experiments

The methodology involved six different experiments to establish the performance of CPM built by the model according to Algorithm 1 and as diagrammatically depicted in Figure 1.

Five popular decision tree algorithms were used as a basis for comparison with the CPM, that is, C5.0, C4.5, RandomForest, REPtree and J48.

Experiment 1: Number of Rules induced Before and After Pruning.

The experiment was to show the level of representations in the heart of the data by the model.

Experiment 2: Depth of Trees After Pruning.

This observation describes the level of simplicity of the model after application of pruning technique.

Experiment 3: Comparative Specificity and Sensitivity Results of classifiers.

The sensitivity and specificity, that is, the recall and precision values respectively form the basis of the confusion matrix which was adjudged the best criteria to check the performance of a classifier (Sarang, 2018). These values explained the level of accurate classification of the sample test.

Experiment 4: Running Time (Training and Predicting Time).

At this stage of the experiment, the time of response of the models to train and predict both known and unknown cases were recorded across all classifiers for comparison.

Experiment 5: The value of F-Score.

The state of the potency of the algorithms was examined with the f-score values which were factors of both recall and precision values.

Experiment 6: Percentage of Prediction of Accuracy

The level of the classifiers accuracies was observed to determine their efficiencies.

3.3 Experiments Implementation Environment:

The implementation of these experiments was done on a machine running Linux operation system and Netbeans as an editor for the Java programming language adopted. A relational database MySQL was used with seven tables and four views to house the training data set and the relationships between them. However, the extracted rules from the forests were also kept in separate table. The output of the model was compared to the classification algorithms in WEKA and R classification packages.

3.4 Performance Measures:

The performance of the new model was carried out with these six measurements:

- (a) Number of Rules induced Before and After Pruning: The number of rules extracted is equivalent to the number of braches in a model. The higher the number of the rules, the lower the level of pruning in a model. A good pruning technique will produce relatively smaller branches.
- (b) Depth of the tree: It helps to show the length of each of the branches in the model of classification. The longer the length of branches in a model the more difficult it is to interpret.
- (c) Recall and Precision Results of Classifiers: When the recall is high and precision is low; it implies that most of the positives is correctly classified (low False Negative, FN) but there are a lot of false positives and when the recall is low and precision is high; it means that a lot of missed positives exist (high FN) but those that were predicted as positives are indeed positive (low False Positives, FP).
- (d) Running Time: The time it takes to train and predict unknown cases was examined which is crucial to the quality of a good model. The shorter the time it takes to

perform the operations, the better it is to manage computing resources.

- (e) The value of F-Score: This denotes how potent a model is in classifying the training samples accurately. When the percentage of classification is higher, it signifies a good model.
- (f) Accuracy: The accuracy of a model in prediction of unknown cases indicates the degree of performance of a classifier. The higher the accuracy in prediction, the better the model in forecasting the future accurately.

4.0 Results and Discussion

4.1: Major Results

(a) Number of Rules induced Before and After Pruning

Figure 2 shows CPM algorithm produced the highest number of rules after training with 96 rules and had 27 rules, the lowest after the application of pruning technique.

Figure 2: Depth of Trees After Pruning

(b) Depth of the tree after Pruning

Figure 3, shows the depth of the models on 1,000 and 2,000 instances in order to demonstrate the effect of volume on the model performance. The CPM model had the least depth on both with 6:9 closely followed by C5.0 with 6:10 depths.

Figure 3: Depth of Trees After Pruning

(c) **Comparative Specificity and Sensitivity Results**

Table 2 shows CPM model having the highest specificity of 0.9916 and sensitivity of 0.9944 while C5.0 was very close in performance with 0.9691 and 0.9916.

Table 2: Comparative Specificity and Sensitivity Results

Model	Recall	Precision
	$\frac{TP}{TP + FN}$	$\frac{TP}{TP + FP}$
RandomForest	0.9691	0.9773
C5.0	0.9691	0.9916
REPTree	0.9665	0.9719
J48	0.9268	0.9320
CPM	0.9916	0.9944

(d) **Running Time (second)**

The time it takes to training and test 500 and 2,000 instances were recorded. The C5.0 recorded the fastest times in both sets with 0.020 and 0.088 seconds while CPM ran for 0.023 and 0.092 seconds as illustrated in Figure 4.

Figure 4: Running Time(second)

(e) The value of F-Score

Table 3, shows the strength of classifiers with the CPM model produced the highest value of f-score; 0.9930 and closely followed by C5.0 with 0.9888.

Table 3: The value of F-Score

Model	Recall	Precision	F-Score
	$\frac{TP}{TP + FN}$	$\frac{TP}{TP + FP}$	$\frac{2 * Recall * Precision}{Recall + Precision}$
RandomForest	0.9691	0.9773	0.9732
C5.0	0.9691	0.9916	0.9888
REPTree	0.9665	0.9719	0.9692
J48	0.9268	0.9320	0.9294
CPM	0.9916	0.9944	0.9930

(f) Percentage of Prediction of Accuracy

The CPM model had the highest accuracy of 99.1667% followed by C5.0 model with 98.667% as shown in Table 4.

Table 4: Percentage of Prediction of Accuracy

Model					Accuracy
	TP	FP	TN	FN	$\frac{TP + FP}{TP + FP + TN + FN}$
RandomForest	345	8	236	11	96.8333
C5.0	353	3	239	5	98.6667
REPTree	346	10	232	12	96.3333
J48	329	24	221	26	91.6667
CPM	355	2	240	3	99.1667

4.2 Discussion of Results

This work has proved through the six experiments that the new Collaborative Pruning Model (CPM) produced a better performance and efficiency when made to classify unknown cases. The potency of this model was clearly demonstrated in the highest number of rules excavated from the data; the smallest length (depth) of the tree after pruning which shows its simplicity; the highest performance in classification of test set which was indicated by the highest values of recall, precision as well as the F-score; although algorithm C5.0 was slightly better off in terms of response time probably because it lacks an additional layer of optimization. Ultimately, the CPM model had a better accuracy value of 0.98% better than the closest model C5.0 in relation to accuracy ranking.

This result agrees with Abu (2012) and Al-Behadili *et al.*, (2018) who asserted that model that combines algorithms often performed better than a solo algorithm and that Ant Colony Optimisation technique has the ability to handle complex tasks.

4.3 Limitation of these Results

The study was limited by the size of the instances available during these experiments. It may be a good idea to test the behaviours of the algorithm when faced with big data.

5.0 Conclusion

The most difficult thing in life is the choice of making the right decision at the most appropriate time. The need to provide a procedure that accurately provides a genuine relationship that lies at the heart of the high volume data is of importance. Thus, this research work has combined C5.0 pessimistic pruning method, Rule-based and Ant Colony Optimisation to improve classifier outcome. This is achieved by producing optimised rules and removing the unwanted representations, which later enhanced classification computing resources management techniques (running time and memory management) as seen in the results produced in training and predicting time, rule induction and size of trees generated, branch duplication identification). Above all, a more accurate algorithm was developed to help in analysing and predicting unknown cases.

In the future, we intend to improve on this model by fine-tuning the number of trees in the forest using different sizes when applying larger data set to determine its level of effectiveness in managing computing resources.

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